

UDC 616.98:578.834]-092-036.882-085.273+615.357

DOI: 10.15587/2519-4798.2021.241456

CURRENT CONCEPTION ABOUT THE PATHOGENESIS AND INTENSIVE CARE OF SEVERE COVID-19 (REVIEW)

Marine Georgiyants, Volodymyr Korsunov, Sergii Dubrov, Oleg Loskutov, Nataliia Bohuslavskaya, Vadim Nikonov, Lidiya Cherkashyna, Oleksiy Oparin, Pavel Nartov, Maksym Holianishchev

The aim of the research. The aim of this work was to summarize the scientific literature data on the pathogenesis and intensive care of the severe course of coronavirus infection.

Materials and methods. Databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus and Web Of Science 2020–2021 were used for literary searches.

Results. An intense inflammatory response against the SARS-CoV-2 virus in COVID-19 patients causes a cytokine storm and hypercoagulability with the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and multiple organ failure. Approximately 17 % to 35 % of hospitalized patients with COVID-19 are treated in the intensive care unit, most often due to hypoxemic respiratory failure and the development of ARDS, and between 29 % and 91 % of patients in intensive care units require invasive ventilation.

In addition to acute respiratory failure, hospitalized patients may have acute renal failure (9 %), liver dysfunction (19 %), coagulation disorders (10–25 %), and septic shock (6 %).

More than 75 % of hospitalized patients require additional oxygen therapy. Respiratory support could vary from the need for oxygen supplementation through a nasal catheter to invasive ventilation or extracorporeal membrane oxygenation in patients with the most severe ARDS.

The uncontrolled inflammation and coagulation seen in COVID-19 patients is similar to multifactorial ARDS, where a plethora of evidence has demonstrated the ability of long-term corticosteroid therapy (CST) to reduce inflammation-coagulation-fibroproliferation and accelerate recovery.

With regard to the assessment of the benefits of therapeutic anticoagulation in patients with elevated D-dimer, the question has not yet been finally resolved, and research devoted to this is still ongoing.

Conclusions. The approaches to respiratory, anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory therapy in critically ill patients with COVID-19 require further research to determine the optimal treatment tactics

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, acute respiratory failure, acute respiratory distress syndrome, respiratory therapy, corticosteroid therapy

How to cite:

Georgiyants, M., Korsunov, V., Dubrov, S., Loskutov, O., Bohuslavskaya, N., Nikonov, V., Cherkashyna, L., Oparin, O., Nartov, P., Holianishchev, M. (2021). Current conception about the pathogenesis and intensive care of severe COVID-19 (review). ScienceRise: Medical Science, 5 (44), 4–9. doi: <http://doi.org/10.15587/2519-4798.2021.241456>

© The Author(s) 2021

This is an open access article under the Creative Commons CC BY license hydrate

1. Introduction

The new coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has spread worldwide, causing thousands of cases of acute respiratory failure with a high mortality rate [1, 2].

On March 14, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared a coronavirus outbreak with a confirmed pandemic in 127 countries. The incidence of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) in COVID-19 infection ranged from 17 % to 41 % [3, 4]. That is why the study of the pathogenesis and intensive care of severe coronavirus infection remains relevant for the timely provision of medical care to patients.

The aim of this work was to summarize the data of the scientific literature on the pathogenesis and intensive care of severe coronavirus infection.

2. Materials and methods

Databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus and Web Of Science were used to search for litera-

ture, where the results of research published in 2020–2021 were found.

3. Results

SARS-CoV-2 virus, the causative agent of COVID-19, belongs to the family coronaviridae, has a diameter of 60 nm to 140 nm and characteristic adhesions in the range from 9 nm to 12 nm, giving virions the appearance of a solar corona. Structurally, it consists of single-stranded RNA. The viral genome lies within the envelope, the glycoproteins of which are crucial for the virus to enter the host cell. The SARS-CoV-2 adhesion protein (SARS) is related to the angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE-2) receptor, which is used by the virus to enter the cell. Due to genetic recombination and variation, coronaviruses could adapt and infect new hosts [5–8].

At the onset of infection, SARS-CoV-2 targets cells, such as nasal and bronchial epithelial cells and

pneumocytes, through a viral structural adhesion protein (S) that binds to the receptor (ACE-2). Transmembrane serine protease type 2 (TMPRSS-2), present in the host cell, promotes virus uptake by cleavage of ACE-2 and activation of protein S, which mediates the penetration of coronavirus into host cells. ACE-2 and TMPRSS-2 are expressed in host target cells, especially in type II alveolar epithelial cells. Like other respiratory viral diseases, such as influenza, profound lymphopenia can occur in individuals with COVID-19 when SARS-CoV-2 infects and kills T lymphocyte cells. In addition, a viral inflammatory response consisting of both an innate and an adaptive immune response (including humoral and cell-mediated immunity) impairs lymphopoiesis and increases lymphocyte apoptosis [9, 10].

In the later stages of infection, when virus replication is accelerated, the integrity of the epithelial-endothelial barrier is disrupted. In addition to epithelial cells, SARS-CoV-2 infects endothelial cells of the pulmonary capillaries, enhancing the inflammatory response and causing an influx of monocytes and neutrophils. Autopsy studies have shown diffuse thickening of the alveolar wall by mononuclear cells and macrophages that penetrate the airspace in addition to endothelium.

Interstitial mononuclear inflammatory infiltrates and edema develop and appear as “frosted glass” on computed tomography (CT) [11].

Intense inflammatory response against the virus in patients with COVID-19 causes a storm of cytokines and hypercoagulation with the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome and multiorgan failure [12].

Patients have endothelial dysfunction with a thrombo-inflammatory condition. Pulmonary microthrombosis and endothelial damage lead to V/Q mismatch (ventilation/perfusion), hypoxemia, and vasodilation [13].

Cytokine storm is characterized by hyperproduction of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines (tumor necrosis factor alpha, interleukin-6 and interleukin- β). Lymphocytopenia is one of the characteristic features of the cytokine storm. In critically ill patients, the level of C-reactive protein, pro-calcitonin, D-dimer and ferritin is markedly elevated and is associated with a poor prognosis [14, 15].

Bradykinin-dependent angioneurotic pulmonary edema may contribute to disease progression. In combination, endothelial barrier integrity and alveolar-capillary oxygen diffusion are characteristic features of COVID-19 [16].

The pathophysiology of COVID-19 is complex, and the disease could compromise the lungs, heart, brain, liver, kidneys, and coagulation system. In severe COVID-19 there is a fulminant activation of coagulation and consumption of coagulation factors. A report from Wuhan (China) states that 71 % of the 183 people who died from COVID-19 met the criteria for diffuse intravascular coagulation [17, 18].

COVID-19 could cause myocarditis, cardiomyopathy, ventricular arrhythmias, acute coronary syndrome, and shock [19–21].

Venous and arterial thromboembolic events are observed in 31–59 % of hospitalized patients with COVID-19.

Patients with comorbidities are highly prone to develop cytokine storm. Concomitant diseases, such as

hypertension, coronary heart disease and diabetes, are associated with a higher risk of death [22].

Common clinical signs of COVID-19 are cough, shortness of breath and fever [23–25].

Additional symptoms such as weakness, fatigue, myalgia, headache, anosmia and ageusia, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea have also been reported commonly [26].

Approximately 17 % to 35 % of hospitalized patients with COVID-19 are treated in the intensive care unit, most often due to hypoxemic respiratory failure and the development of ARDS. Among patients in intensive care units with COVID-19, 29 % to 91 % require invasive lung ventilation [25, 27, 28].

ARDS is defined as a form of inflammatory pulmonary edema of noncardiogenic etiology with a decrease in areas of normoventilated lung and, as a consequence, is characterized by a decrease in respiratory compliance and the effect of shunting.

The Berlin definition proposes ARDS categories based on the degree of hypoxemia: mild ($200 \text{ mm Hg} < \text{PaO}_2/\text{FIO}_2 \leq 300 \text{ mm Hg}$), moderate ($100 \text{ mm Hg} < \text{PaO}_2/\text{FIO}_2 \leq 200 \text{ mm Hg}$) and severe ($\text{PaO}_2/\text{FIO}_2 \leq 100 \text{ mm Hg}$), and 4 auxiliary variables for severe ARDS: radiographic severity, respiratory compliance ($\leq 40 \text{ ml/cm H}_2\text{O}$), positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) $10 \text{ cm H}_2\text{O}$ and adjusted expiratory volume per minute ($\geq 10 \text{ l/min}$) [29].

Patients with severe COVID-19 usually have tachypnea (respiratory rate ≥ 30 breaths per minute), decreased saturation (oxygen saturation $\leq 93 \%$), and pulmonary infiltrates $>50 \%$ (according to CT data) [30].

A group of experts suggests that COVID may have two ARDS phenotypes [31].

In the first phenotype, patients often show normal compliance even with severe hypoxemia, with normal or even increased minute ventilation, and more than half of these patients do not have shortness of breath (“silent hypoxemia”). Radiographically, such patients have tomographic lesions in the form of “frosted glass”, which indicate interstitial and non-alveolar edema, and at this stage the infiltrates are relatively limited. These patients are referred to as “type L” (“low elastance”), with the additional main characteristics of high compliance, limited response to changes in PEEP and low lung mass, assessed by chest CT.

In the second phenotype, the patient's condition may improve clinically or, due to individual factors or inadequate treatment, evolve into a more severe form close to classical ARDS. This is called “type H” (from “high elastance, high elasticity”), which also demonstrates low compliance, better sensitivity to changes in PEEP and high lung mass, assessed on chest CT [32].

In addition to acute respiratory failure (ARF), hospitalized patients may develop acute renal failure (9%), liver dysfunction (19%), coagulation disorders (10–25%) and septic shock (6%) [33–35].

Regarding the treatment of patients with COVID-19, more than 75 % of hospitalized patients require additional oxygen therapy. Respiratory support may differ from the need to add oxygen through a nasal catheter to invasive pulmonary ventilation or extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) in patients with the most severe form of ARDS. In general, patients should receive

a minimum amount of additional O₂ to achieve a SpO₂ level of 92 to 96 %. Without the analysis of blood gases, the degree of hypoxemia can be assessed by the ratio of SpO₂/FiO₂, the value of which ≤ 315 indicates ARDS [36].

The COVID-19 pandemic has revealed the continuing uncertainty and implications of discussions about whether patients with significant hypoxemia should use an early intubation strategy or, conversely, a conservative non-invasive approach [33, 37, 38].

Some studies demonstrate the potential beneficial effects of HFNO (high-flow nasal oxygenation) in the context of acute respiratory failure associated with COVID-19, and support recent evidence that HFNO is associated with a reduced risk of intubation in this group of patients [39].

Many hospitals use non-invasive ventilation (NIV) as an attempt to prevent the development of severe respiratory failure, which requires invasive ventilation support. The European Society of Intensive Care Medicine (ESICM) and the National Health Service of England (NHS-England) recommend the use of NIV as an initial measure for respiratory failure in patients with COVID-19. In the vast majority of cases, COVID-19 used the mode of continuous positive airways pressure, CPAP, (average values of about 10 cm H₂O), which is due to its relatively high efficiency in ARF [40].

In some studies, prone-position in non-intubated patients has significantly improved oxygenation [41, 42].

In severe cases of respiratory failure, as seen with COVID-19, hypoxemia may lead to a sustained increase in respiratory effort resulting in self-inflicted lung injury (P-SILI). In addition, other factors, such as fluid overload or myocardial damage caused by SARS-CoV-2, may also play an important role in the deterioration of the condition due to pulmonary congestion [43].

The intubation threshold for respiratory failure associated with COVID-19 is controversial, as many patients have normal respiratory function but severe hypoxemia [44].

As for the strategy of mechanical ventilation, it should take into account the different mechanisms of lung damage and different manifestations of the disease, i.e. the ARDS phenotype.

L-type patients, usually patients with good pulmonary compliance, are recommended to be ventilated with a larger tidal volume (about 7–8 ml / kg of ideal body weight) and a PEEP of 8 to 10 cm H₂O to avoid redirection of blood flow from aerated pulmonary capillaries, which may increase the effect of shunting.

With disease progression and worsening of inflammatory edema, the patient may switch to “type H”. The pathophysiology of this progression is probably the result of a combination of factors: in addition to self-induced lesion (P-SILI), the viral lesion itself leads to uncontrolled inflammation and edema, with local and generalized thrombogenesis, intense cytokine release and right ventricular overload. The formed pulmonary edema is close to the classical representation of ARDS, with collapsed alveoli and large normoperfusion and hypo-aerated areas. In these more advanced cases, the mechanical ventilation strategy should be more traditional: elevated

PEEP, VT<6 ml/kg, prone position and alveolar recruitment manoeuvres [32].

Regarding the etiotropic therapy of COVID-19, currently the most promising antiviral drug is remdesivir. After several large-scale clinical trials of remdesivir, despite the ambiguity of the available results, on May 1, 2020, the FDA (food and drug administration) granted emergency use of remdesivir for the treatment of COVID-19 in the United States [45].

Remdesivir is an adenosine nucleotide prodrug that is metabolized in body cells to form a pharmacologically active adenosine triphosphate analogue that inhibits viral RNA polymerases. Previous studies have shown that remdesivir has in vitro activity against Ebola and several coronaviruses, demonstrating prophylactic and therapeutic efficacy in non-clinical models [46, 47].

Remdesivir is included in the treatment protocols of COVID-19 in Ukraine, according to which on the first day – a loading dose of 200 mg once a day (iv for 30–120 minutes), on the second day – a maintenance dose of 100 mg once a day (in / for 30–120 minutes) [48].

Of course, the maximum effect of remdesivir is seen in the early stages of the disease [49], whereas in hospitalized patients, anti-inflammatory drugs may be useful to prevent disease progression, and anticoagulants to prevent thromboembolic complications.

The uncontrolled inflammation and coagulation observed in patients with COVID-19 [50] is similar to multifactorial ARDS, where much evidence has demonstrated the ability of long-term corticosteroid therapy (CST) to reduce inflammation-coagulation-fibroproliferation and accelerate recovery [51].

A study by Chinese scientists showed that COVID-19, associated with increased levels of cytokines, resembles secondary hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis, a condition that responds to CST [4].

Although some recommendations were against the use of corticosteroids [52, 53], dexamethasone (6 mg/day) in the RECOVERY study reduced mortality among those receiving invasive mechanical ventilation or oxygen alone [54].

Dexamethasone is officially approved for the treatment of COVID-19 in many countries, including Ukraine. It is not specific (antiviral), but it has been tested and is effective in suppressing the patient's hyperimmune response to the virus. Methylprednisolone is also used, including as a pulse therapy for critical patients [48].

A meta-analysis of 60 studies with 31,732 patients was performed. The included trials were classified into trials that included only steroid therapy and those that included steroids in addition to other standard treatments. As for steroid treatment, the most common steroid is methylprednisolone (used in 28 trials) at different doses depending on the age of the patients. The maximum loading dose of methylprednisolone used was 500 mg intravenously for 1 hour in the study (IRCT20080901001165N52). Steroids were given for a minimum of 3 days to a maximum of 21 days. Other steroids used are budesonide, ciclesonide, dexamethasone, formoterol, prednisolone, prednisone and hydrocortisone. Their safety and efficacy in the treatment of COVID-19 symptoms, especially in the pneumonia

stage, have been tested. The trials also included patients of different age groups at different stages of COVID-19.

Corticosteroids can regulate immune-mediated lung damage and reduce its development to respiratory failure and death. Dexamethasone has been reported to reduce the duration of mechanical ventilation. Glucocorticoid therapy has shown a significant improvement in the permeability of the alveolar-capillary membrane and mediators of inflammation and tissue repair. The results of these tests show promising results and recommend the use of methylprednisolone and dexamethasone in severe COVID-19. It is likely that certain corticosteroid treatments may have differences in efficacy depending on the stage of the disease and in different manifestations of the disease [55].

Therefore, based on the above, systemic corticosteroids are the only treatment that reduces mortality in randomized controlled clinical trials in patients with severe COVID-19. Despite these data, there are still many questions about the use of immunosuppressants in these patients. The incidence of secondary infections during corticosteroid therapy in patients with COVID-19 is unknown, although information on this side effect has been reported in the scientific literature on influenza. Observational studies of other immunomodulatory agents, such as tocilizumab, have shown conflicting results and also suggest an increased risk of secondary infections [56].

Further reliable randomized controlled trials of these drugs are expected, but systemic corticosteroids are currently the mainstay of treatment for severe COVID-19 disease to alleviate cytokine storms.

Of course, anticoagulant therapy plays an important role in the treatment of patients with COVID-19. Many studies are devoted to this area, some of them are quite long. In particular, the issue of prescribing appropriate doses of anticoagulants in critically ill patients should be addressed.

Prevention of thromboembolic events by subcutaneous low molecular weight heparin is recommended for all hospitalized patients with COVID-19 [18, 48, 35].

However, the question of evaluating the benefits of therapeutic anticoagulation in certain patients (i.e., those with elevated D-dimer) has not yet been definitively resolved, and studies are still ongoing.

4. Conclusions

Therefore, the range of complications with COVID-19 is very wide, which may be due to hypoxia, coagulopathy, “cytokine storm”, as well as the combined effect of these factors, which determines the need for early diagnosis, the use of effective therapy and a multidisciplinary approach for better outcomes in patients with COVID-19.

Approaches to respiratory, anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory therapy in severe patients with COVID-19 require further research to determine the optimal treatment tactics.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Financing

The study was performed without financial support.

References

- Zhou, F., Yu, T., Du, R., Fan, G., Liu, Y., Liu, Z. et al. (2020). Clinical course and risk factors for mortality of adult inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study. *The Lancet*, 395 (10229), 1054–1062. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30566-3](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30566-3)
- Karagiannidis, C., Mostert, C., Hentschker, C., Voshaar, T., Malzahn, J., Schillinger, G. et al. (2020). Case characteristics, resource use, and outcomes of 10 021 patients with COVID-19 admitted to 920 German hospitals: an observational study. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 8 (9), 853–862. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30316-7](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30316-7)
- Chen, N., Zhou, M., Dong, X., Qu, J., Gong, F., Han, Y. et al. (2020). Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 99 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a descriptive study. *The Lancet*, 395 (10223), 507–513. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30211-7](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30211-7)
- Huang, C., Wang, Y., Li, X., Ren, L., Zhao, J., Hu, Y. et al. (2020). Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *The Lancet*, 395 (10223), 497–506. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30183-5](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30183-5)
- Li, M.-Y., Li, L., Zhang, Y., Wang, X.-S. (2020). Expression of the SARS-CoV-2 cell receptor gene ACE2 in a wide variety of human tissues. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, 9 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-020-00662-x>
- Puelles, V. G., Lütgehetmann, M., Lindenmeyer, M. T., Sperhake, J. P., Wong, M. N., Allweiss, L. et al. (2020). Multiorgan and Renal Tropism of SARS-CoV-2. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 383 (6), 590–592. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1056/nejmc2011400>
- Goldsmith, C. S., Tatti, K. M., Ksiazek, T. G., Rollin, P. E., Comer, J. A., Lee, W. W. et al. (2004). Ultrastructural Characterization of SARS Coronavirus. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 10 (2), 320–326. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3201/eid1002.030913>
- Lu, R., Zhao, X., Li, J., Niu, P., Yang, B., Wu, H. et al. (2020). Genomic characterisation and epidemiology of 2019 novel coronavirus: implications for virus origins and receptor binding. *The Lancet*, 395 (10224), 565–574. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30251-8](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30251-8)
- Hoffmann, M., Kleine-Weber, H., Schroeder, S., Krüger, N., Herrler, T., Erichsen, S. et al. (2020). SARS-CoV-2 Cell Entry Depends on ACE2 and TMPRSS2 and Is Blocked by a Clinically Proven Protease Inhibitor. *Cell*, 181 (2), 271–280. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.02.052>
- Sungnak, W., Huang, N., Bécavin, C., Berg, M., Queen, R. et al. (2020). SARS-CoV-2 entry factors are highly expressed in nasal epithelial cells together with innate immune genes. *Nature Medicine*, 26 (5), 681–687. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0868-6>
- Xu, Z., Shi, L., Wang, Y., Zhang, J., Huang, L., Zhang, C. et al. (2020). Pathological findings of COVID-19 associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 8 (4), 420–422. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30076-x](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30076-x)
- Jose, R. J., Manuel, A. (2020). COVID-19 cytokine storm: the interplay between inflammation and coagulation. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 8 (6), e46–e47. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30216-2](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30216-2)
- Ciceri, F., Beretta, L., Scandroglio, A. M., Colombo, S. et al. (2020). Microvascular COVID-19 lung vessels obstructive thromboinflammatory syndrome (MicroCLOTS): an atypical acute respiratory distress syndrome working hypothesis. *Critical Care and Resuscitation*, 22 (2), 95–97. doi: <http://doi.org/10.51893/2020.2.pov2>
- Coperchini, F., Chiovato, L., Croce, L., Magri, F., Rotondi, M. (2020). The cytokine storm in COVID-19: An overview of the involvement of the chemokine/chemokine-receptor system. *Cytokine & Growth Factor Reviews*, 53, 25–32. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.cytogfr.2020.05.003>

15. Manjili, R. H., Zarei, M., Habibi, M., Manjili, M. H. (2020). COVID-19 as an Acute Inflammatory Disease. *The Journal of Immunology*, 205 (1), 12–19. doi: <http://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.2000413>
16. Van de Veerdonk, F. L., Netea, M. G., van Deuren, M., van der Meer, J. W., de Mast, Q., Brüggemann, R. J., van der Hoeven, H. (2020). Kallikrein-kinin blockade in patients with COVID-19 to prevent acute respiratory distress syndrome. *eLife*, 9. doi: <http://doi.org/10.7554/elife.57555>
17. Tang, N., Li, D., Wang, X., Sun, Z. (2020). Abnormal coagulation parameters are associated with poor prognosis in patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 18 (4), 844–847. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1111/jth.14768>
18. Thachil, J., Tang, N., Gando, S., Falanga, A., Cattaneo, M., Levi, M. et al. (2020). ISTH interim guidance on recognition and management of coagulopathy in COVID-19. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 18 (5), 1023–1026. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1111/jth.14810>
19. Wiersinga, W. J., Rhodes, A., Cheng, A. C., Peacock, S. J., Prescott, H. C. (2020). Pathophysiology, Transmission, Diagnosis, and Treatment of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *JAMA*, 324 (8), 782. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.12839>
20. Vincent, J-L., Slutsky, A. S. (2020). Coronavirus: just imagine.... *Critical Care*, 24 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-020-2824-8>
21. Costa, I., Bittar, C. S., Rizk, S. I., Araújo Filho, A. E., Santos, K. A. Q., Machado, T. I. V. et al. (2020). The heart and COVID-19: what cardiologists need to know. *Arq Bras Cardiol*, 114 (5), 805–816. doi: <http://doi.org/10.36660/abc.20200279>
22. Berger, J. R. (2020). COVID-19 and the nervous system. *Journal of NeuroVirology*, 26 (2), 143–148. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s13365-020-00840-5>
23. Fraissé, M., Logre, E., Pajot, O., Mentec, H., Plantefève, G., Contou, D. (2020). Thrombotic and hemorrhagic events in critically ill COVID-19 patients: a French monocenter retrospective study. *Critical Care*, 24 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-020-03025-y>
24. Klok, F. A., Kruip, M. J. H. A., van der Meer, N. J. M., Arbous, M. S., Gommers, D. A. M. P. J., Kant, K. M. et al. (2020). Incidence of thrombotic complications in critically ill ICU patients with COVID-19. *Thrombosis Research*, 191, 145–147. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2020.04.013>
25. Docherty, A. B., Harrison, E. M., Green, C. A., Hardwick, H. E., Pius, R., Norman, L. et al. (2020). Features of 20 133 UK patients in hospital with covid-19 using the ISARIC WHO Clinical Characterisation Protocol: prospective observational cohort study. *BMJ*, 369, 1985. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1985>
26. Lapostolle, F., Schneider, E., Vianu, I., Dollet, G., Roche, B., Berdah, J. et al. (2020). Clinical features of 1487 COVID-19 patients with outpatient management in the Greater Paris: the COVID-call study. *Internal and Emergency Medicine*, 15 (5), 813–817. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-020-02379-z>
27. Grasselli, G., Zangrillo, A., Zanella, A., Antonelli, M., Cabrini, L., Castelli, A. et al. (2020). Baseline Characteristics and Outcomes of 1591 Patients Infected With SARS-CoV-2 Admitted to ICUs of the Lombardy Region, Italy. *JAMA*, 323 (16), 1574–1581. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.5394>
28. Myers, L. C., Parodi, S. M., Escobar, G. J., Liu, V. X. (2020). Characteristics of Hospitalized Adults With COVID-19 in an Integrated Health Care System in California. *JAMA*, 323 (21), 2195–2198. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.7202>
29. Force, A. D. T., Ranieri, V. M., Rubenfeld, G. D., Thompson, B. T., Ferguson, N. D., Caldwell, E. et al. (2012). Acute respiratory distress syndrome: the Berlin Definition. *JAMA*, 307 (23), 2526–2533. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2012.5669>
30. Wu, Z., McGoogan, J. M. (2020). Characteristics of and important lessons from the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak in China: summary of a report of 72314 cases from the Chinese center for disease control and prevention. *JAMA*, 323 (13), 1239. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.2648>
31. Gattinoni, L., Chiumello, D., Caironi, P., Busana, M., Romitti, F., Brazzi, L., Camporota, L. (2020). COVID-19 pneumonia: different respiratory treatments for different phenotypes? *Intensive Care Medicine*, 46 (6), 1099–1102. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-020-06033-2>
32. Marini, J. J., Gattinoni, L. (2020). Management of COVID-19 Respiratory Distress. *JAMA*, 323 (22), 2329–2330. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.6825>
33. Mao, R., Qiu, Y., He, J.-S., Tan, J.-Y., Li, X.-H., Liang, J. et al. (2020). Manifestations and prognosis of gastrointestinal and liver involvement in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Gastroenterology & Hepatology*, 5 (7), 667–678. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-1253\(20\)30126-6](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-1253(20)30126-6)
34. Levi, M., Thachil, J., Iba, T., Levy, J. H. (2020). Coagulation abnormalities and thrombosis in patients with COVID-19. *The Lancet Haematology*, 7 (6), e438–e440. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-3026\(20\)30145-9](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-3026(20)30145-9)
35. Yang, X., Yu, Y., Xu, J., Shu, H., Xia, J., Liu, H. et al. (2020). Clinical course and outcomes of critically ill patients with SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a single-centered, retrospective, observational study. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 8 (5), 475–481. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30079-5](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30079-5)
36. Rice, T. W., Wheeler, A. P., Bernard, G. R., Hayden, D. L., Schoenfeld, D. A., Ware, L. B. (2007). Comparison of the SpO₂/FIO₂ ratio and the PaO₂/FIO₂ ratio in patients with acute lung injury or ARDS. *Chest*, 132 (2), 410–417. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1378/chest.07-0617>
37. Tobin, M. J., Laghi, F., Jubran, A. (2020). Caution about early intubation and mechanical ventilation in COVID-19. *Annals of Intensive Care*, 10 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1186/s13613-020-00692-6>
38. Rola, P., Farkas, J., Spiegel, R., Kyle-Sidell, C., Weingart, S., Duggan, L. et al. (2020). Rethinking the early intubation paradigm of COVID-19: time to change gears? *Clinical and Experimental Emergency Medicine*, 7 (2), 78–80. doi: <http://doi.org/10.15441/ceem.20.043>
39. Demoule, A., Vieillard Baron, A., Darmon, M., Beurton, A., Géri, G., Voiriot, G. et al. (2020). High-Flow Nasal Cannula in Critically Ill Patients with Severe COVID-19. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 202 (7), 1039–1042. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.202005-20071e>
40. Alhazzani, W., Møller, M. H., Arabi, Y. M., Loeb, M., Gong, M. N., Fan, E. et al. (2020). Surviving Sepsis Campaign: guidelines on the management of critically ill adults with Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Intensive Care Medicine*, 46 (5), 854–887. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-020-06022-5>
41. Elharrar, X., Trigui, Y., Dols, A.-M., Touchon, F., Martinez, S., Prud'homme, E., Papazian, L. (2020). Use of Prone Positioning in Nonintubated Patients With COVID-19 and Hypoxemic Acute Respiratory Failure. *JAMA*, 323 (22), 2336–2338. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.8255>
42. Coppo, A., Bellani, G., Winterton, D., Di Pierro, M., Soria, A., Favero, P. et al. (2020). Feasibility and physiological effects of prone positioning in non-intubated patients with acute respiratory failure due to COVID-19 (PRON-COVID): a prospective cohort study. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 8 (8), 765–774. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600\(20\)30268-x](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-2600(20)30268-x)
43. Sorbello, M., El-Boghdady, K., Di Giacinto, I., Cataldo, R., Esposito, C. et al. (2020). The Italian coronavirus disease 2019 outbreak: recommendations from clinical practice. *Anaesthesia*, 75 (6), 724–732. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1111/anae.15049>
44. Tobin, M. J. (2020). Basing Respiratory Management of COVID-19 on Physiological Principles. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 201 (11), 1319–1320. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.202004-1076ed>

45. Coronavirus (COVID-19) Update: FDA Issues Emergency Use Authorization for Potential COVID-19 Treatment (2020). Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/coronavirus-covid-19-update-fda-issues-emergency-use-authorization-potential-covid-19-treatment>
46. De Wit, E., Feldmann, F., Cronin, J., Jordan, R., Okumura, A., Thomas, T. et. al. (2020). Prophylactic and therapeutic remdesivir (GS-5734) treatment in the rhesus macaque model of MERS-CoV infection. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117 (12), 6771–6776. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1922083117>
47. Sheahan, T. P., Sims, A. C., Leist, S. R., Schäfer, A., Won, J., Brown, A. J. et. al. (2020). Comparative therapeutic efficacy of remdesivir and combination lopinavir, ritonavir, and interferon beta against MERS-CoV. *Nature Communications*, 11 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13940-6>
48. Протокол «Nadannia medychnoi dopomohy dlia likuvannia koronavirusnoi khvoroby (COVID-19)» (2021). Nakaz MOZ Ukrainy No. 638. 06.04.2021. Available at: <https://moz.gov.ua/article/ministry-mandates/nakaz-moz-ukraini-vid-06042021--638-provnesennja-zmin-do-protokolu--nadannja-medichnoi-dopomogi-dlja-likuvannja--koronavirusnoi-hvorobi-covid-19>
49. NIH Clinical Trial Shows Remdesivir Accelerates Recovery from Advanced COVID-19 (2020). Available at: <https://www.niaid.nih.gov/news-events/nih-clinical-trial-shows-remdesivir-accelerates-recovery-advanced-covid-19>
50. Mehta, P., McAuley, D. F., Brown, M., Sanchez, E., Tattersall, R. S., Manson, J. J. (2020). COVID-19: consider cytokine storm syndromes and immunosuppression. *The Lancet*, 395 (10229), 1033–1034. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30628-0](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30628-0)
51. Meduri, G. U., Annane, D., Chrousos, G. P., Marik, P. E., Sinclair, S. E. (2009). Activation and Regulation of Systemic Inflammation in ARDS. *Chest*, 136 (6), 1631–1643. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1378/chest.08-2408>
52. Bhimraj, A., Morgan, R. L., Shumaker, A. H., Laverne, V., Baden, L., Cheng, V. C.-C. et. al. (2020). Infectious Diseases Society of America Guidelines on the Treatment and Management of Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciaa478>
53. COVID-19 Treatment Guidelines Panel Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) treatment guidelines National Institutes of Health (2020). Available at: <https://www.covid19treatmentguidelines.nih.gov/>
54. Horby, P., Lim, W. S., Emberson, J., Mafham, M., Bell, J. et. al. (2020). Effect of Dexamethasone in Hospitalized Patients with COVID-19 – Preliminary Report. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.22.20137273>
55. Raju, R., V., Prajith, V., Biatris, P. S., Chander J., S. J. U. (2021). Therapeutic role of corticosteroids in COVID-19: a systematic review of registered clinical trials. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 7 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-021-00217-3>
56. Guaraldi, G., Meschiari, M., Cozzi-Lepri, A., Milic, J., Tonelli, R., Menozzi, M. et. al. (2020). Tocilizumab in patients with severe COVID-19: a retrospective cohort study. *The Lancet Rheumatology*, 2 (8), e474–e484. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s2665-9913\(20\)30173-9](http://doi.org/10.1016/s2665-9913(20)30173-9)

Received date 29.07.2021

Accepted date 07.09.2021

Published date 30.09.2021

Marine Georgiyants, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector, Department of Anesthesiology, Pediatric Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Volodymyr Korsunov, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, Pediatric Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Sergii Dubrov, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of Department, Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Bogomolets National Medical University, T. Shevchenko blvd., 13, Kyiv, 01601

Oleg Loskutov, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of "Anesthesiology and Intensive Care", Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine, Dorohozhytska str., 9, Kyiv, Ukraine, 04112

Nataliia Bohuslavska, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, Pediatric Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Vadim Nikonov, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine and Disaster Medicine, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Lidiya Cherkashyna, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of Family Medicine, Folk and Alternative Medicine and Sanology, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Oleksiy Oparin, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of Therapy, Rheumatology and Clinical Pharmacology, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Pavel Nartov, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of Infectious Diseases, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

Maksym Holianishchev, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Kharkiv Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Amosova str., 58, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61176

**Corresponding author: Nataliia Bohuslavska, e-mail: nata-anest-78@ukr.net*